

Reliability comparisons of mobile network operators: An experimental case study from crowdsourced dataset

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Abstract:

It is of great interest for Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) to know how well their network infrastructure performance behaves in different geographical regions of their operating country compared to their horizontal competitors. However, traditional network monitoring and measurement methods of network infrastructure are using limited number of measurement points that are insufficient for detailed analysis and expensive to scale using internal workforce. On the other hand, the abundance of crowd-sourced content can engender various unforeseen opportunities for MNOs to cope with this scaling problem. This paper is investigating end-to-end reliability and packet loss (PL) performance comparisons of MNOs using previously collected real-world proprietary crowd-sourced dataset from user's application for 13 months of duration in Turkey. More particularly, a unified crowd-sourced data aided statistical MNO comparison framework is proposed, which consists of data collection and network performance analysis steps. Our results are statistically supported using confidence interval (CI) analysis for the mean difference of PL ratios and reliability levels of MNOs using unpaired number of observations statistical analysis. The network performance results indicate that significant performance differences on MNOs depending on different regions of the country exist. Moreover, we observe that overall comparative ordered list of MNOs' reliability performance does not differ when both PL and latency requirements vary.

Key words: data analytics, MNOs, statistics, reliability, KPIs.

1. Introduction

Almost all Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) are heavily investing on network infrastructure where necessary changes and technological upgrades have clear impact on their daily end-to-end network performances. However, providing nationwide coverage with high quality Key Performance Indicator (KPI) is not an easy task. Additionally, maintaining better KPI guarantees in some areas will not easily have excellence in other parts of the country (e.g. in urban, suburban or rural areas). As a matter of fact, services on large geographical areas have different network demands and requirements where various technical approaches (e.g. statistics, machine learning) need to be exploited to provision adequately in urban, suburban or rural areas of the country. For example, to support an acceptable Internet connection, services such as voice over IP (VoIP), live streaming (e.g. Youtube or NetFlix), 4K Ultra or full HD Video, online video gaming, instant messaging etc. should be enabled for all MNOs depending on the geographical

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1 locations as well as users' periodic demands on certain times of the day [1].

2 MNO's performances over mobile infrastructure have changed dramatically over the last years and
3 close race between MNOs exists to upgrade into advanced mobile infrastructure. The introduction of 4G
4 and Long Term Evolution Advanced (LTE-A) services has increased subscribers' expectations in terms
5 of data rates, latency and reliability. The network end-to-end performances of different MNOs also differ
6 based on their different investment and management strategies. For example, for some MNOs that are
7 deploying massive Internet of Things (IoT) devices, highly reliable and low block error rate (BLER) data
8 transmission may be of interest whereas for other MNO interested in providing communication for time-
9 critical applications, low latency can be critical. Moreover, those KPI performances of MNOs can differ
10 based on the geographical locations' target metrics and requirements. Some of the important KPIs that
11 are studied within this paper for comparing MNO performances as well as defining target requirements
12 are as follows: **(i) Latency** is the measurement of Round Trip Time (RTT) it takes for one packet sent
13 from user equipment (UE) to reach to application server and then back to UE, **(ii) Packet Loss (PL)**
14 is defined as Lost Data/Total Sent Data which gives the ratio of data packets that are not arriving into
15 the intended destination. **(iii) Reliability** is defined as the average number of correct observations (in
16 percentages) for the given requirements when the amount of β bytes of transmitted data is transmitted
17 with BLER less than λ and within a less than γ ms of latency. In other words, reliability measures
18 providing a high level of correct message transmission within a latency bound. In this paper, we are
19 utilizing the The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)'s reliability definition [2] which is defined
20 as one of the KPIs according to 3GPP's The Fifth Generation (5G) requirements for Ultra reliability and
21 low latency communications (URLLC) use case [3].

22 On the other hand, crowd-sourcing data from masses has also gained a steam in the last few years
23 as desired source of insights [4]. Crowd-sourcing data is differentiated from traditional data collection
24 procedures in many aspects in terms its cost efficiency, frequency, immediacy and usability which may
25 lead to significant potential to MNOs for analyzing their user' behaviours. Together with large number
26 of received network performance observations scattered nationwide, unlocking valuable insights about a
27 recent product, service or brand is possible. This can be helpful to solve large-scale network monitoring
28 problems of MNOs in a cost-effective manner using the power of crowd. For example, analyzing large-scale
29 test results from end-users provides the opportunity to understand network service performance, relate
30 anomalies based on KPIs tests with other dataset (e.g. social media data) and study the evolution of
31 network performance over observation time. For MNOs, this analysis is useful to build accurate models
32 that can help in building smarter next generation infrastructure. Additionally, extracting knowledge from
33 crowd-sourced data is especially valuable as it can enable developing fine-grained business models.

34 To obtain valuable information from wireless 4G cellular networks using crowd-sourced dataset,
35 utilization of appropriate statistical and intelligent analytic techniques is needed. In this light, a natural
36 question arises: How can crowd-sourced data and statistics help to extract insight on performances of each
37 MNOs as well as their competitors' wireless networks? Contributing to the solution of this question, in this
38 paper we utilize real-world proprietary KPI observations dataset that is built by experiments performed
39 by different MNOs's UEs on large-scale geographical locations over a long period of time. Using statistical
40 analysis methods over this dataset, we focus on end-to-end performance comparisons of three major MNOs
41 in Turkey¹. Our results reveal the impact of location based on latency, reliability and PL KPIs of different

¹GSMA (2019). Definitive data and analysis for the mobile industry [online]. Website <https://www.gsmainelligence.com> [accessed 09 October 2019].

1 MNOs that are providing nationwide coverage.

2 1.1. Related Work

3 In this section, we will classify the related works into three broad categories, namely, network performance
4 measurements, crowd-sourced data and reliability aspects.

5 **Network performance measurements:** For extracting knowledge from mobile network performance
6 measurements, there are various works in the literature such as [5–8] for network planning and [9–11] for
7 analyzing KPI performance differences of MNOs. A recent enabler technology that provides low-latency
8 and ultra-high reliable communication services is given in [8]. A coverage analysis based on Base Station
9 (BS) KPIs to reduce drive test and field measurement cost using big data analytics is proposed in [12].
10 A case study targeting dropped calls and bad quality-of-service minimization is provided in [6]. In order
11 to identify variance in end-to-end performance of network behaviour, space and time based properties
12 of network performances of different carriers are analyzed in [9]. The authors in [10] have investigated
13 interactions between radio layers, network protocols and applications and their affects on 4G Long Term
14 Evolution (LTE) network performance. The impact of the packet size on one-way delay for the Download
15 (DL) in 3G mobile networks using measurements from several Swedish mobile operators is shown in [11].
16 In a recent work performed in UK, the authors in [13] show that the network performance effects are quite
17 important and play an important role in terms of end-user’s choice of MNOs. Similarly, the authors in
18 [14] demonstrate the significant positive impact of network effects on the demand for mobile services and
19 end-user’s decisions by analyzing the data from January 1998 to June 2003 in Germany. Experimental
20 results on network performances of twelve commercial mobile operators across Europe are described in [15].
21 Finally, large scale cellular network traffic collected from thousands of BSs for traffic modelling purposes is
22 analyzed in [16]. However, in most of the above cases, network performance measurements and comparisons
23 between MNOs are done either using small-scale dataset collected via experimental trials (such as drive
24 tests with devices capable of collecting KPI data using multiple MNO subscriber identification module
25 (SIM) cards) or lacks appropriate comparative reliability analysis using large-scale crowd-sourced dataset
26 collected from thousands of UEs.

27 **Crowd-sourced data:** Crowd-sourced dataset are useful for the analysis and exploration of the MNOs’
28 performances. There are numerous work employing different aspects of crowd-sourced data for better
29 network optimization inside MNOs [17, 18]. Using Austrian Regulatory Authority for Broadcasting and
30 Telecommunications (RTR) Open Data (a crowd-sourced dataset)², the authors in [17] have investigated
31 the effect of different features that distinguished MNOs with each other. On the other hand, the authors
32 in [18] have used both RTR Nettest and Netradar [19] crowd-sourced dataset to design a feature mapping
33 strategy between those dataset. A set of quality-of-service (QoS)-related metrics which are crowd-sourced
34 from the UEs are used to analyze the MNOs network performances under stringent ElectroMagnetic Field
35 (EMF) constraints and regulations in [20]. The authors in [21] rely on crowd-sourced data to provide
36 coverage maps of different MNOs and also focused on the coverage map accuracy from the perspective
37 of device diversity. Compared to most of the existing analysis that are based on using crowd-sourced
38 dataset, in this work we focus on understanding the comparative behaviours of the performance of MNOs
39 using specific network infrastructure KPIs (e.g. calculated reliability together with packet loss and latency
40 KPIs) at large-scale (i.e. in nationwide locations with thousands of measurements over a long period of
41 duration of major MNOs’ metrics in Turkey).

²NETZTEST (2019). RTR – NetTest [online]. Website <https://www.netztest.at/en/> [accessed 09 October 2019].

1 **Reliability:** Reliability metric has been the focus of 5G era for mission-critical services that require
2 URLLC [22–24]. URLLC cases demand 99.999% network reliability, and 1 ms latency [25]. In general,
3 it specifies that packets are successfully delivered while the latency bound is satisfied. However, other
4 definitions also exist including reliability definition by 3GPP, reliability per node and control channel
5 reliability [2, 8]. A low cost portable measurement framework to quantify the end-to-end latency and
6 reliability metrics of communication links is given in [24]. The authors in [22] have introduced a REliability-
7 Aware service CHaining (REACH) framework to ensure reliable service chaining with Virtual Network
8 Functions (VNFs). In [23], the authors are proposing a softwarized 5G architecture to ensure end-to-end
9 reliability of network services such as mission-critical traffic. Although there has been many works on
10 ensuring reliability aspects for MNOs, no experimental evaluations have been devised for comparisons of
11 different MNOs in terms of their composite metrics such as reliability using crowd-sourced dataset. In our
12 previous related work, we investigated the performance of three MNOs in terms of latency, DL/Upload
13 (UL) speed, jitter and PL [26]. Different than our previous analysis, in this paper we are extending these
14 comparison ideas into combining different metrics to evaluate the performance of MNOs in terms of their
15 reliability.

16 1.2. Our Contributions

17 The statistical comparative performance analysis of major MNOs is still an open and active research
18 area where MNOs, users and service providers are willing to know how well their horizontal and vertical
19 competitors are performing in certain regions of their operating country. In this paper, different than
20 previous works outlined above, we are analyzing the end-to-end performance comparisons of MNOs based
21 on reliability and PL KPIs using statistical confidence interval (CI) for proportions analysis as our basis
22 methodology. Compared to state-of-the-art, our MNO reliability analysis contributions are mainly focusing
23 on real-world proprietary crowd-sourced network performance test dataset collected from thousands of UEs
24 over a period of 13 months in Turkey which are different than pure simulation-based analysis that rely
25 mostly on synthetic data generators. Summary of our key findings are as follows:

- 26 • A framework that invokes statistical techniques using crowd-sourced data and extracts MNO net-
27 works performances in different cities of Turkey is proposed where the visualization is done using
28 Folium visualization tool’s interactive map.
- 29 • Statistical approaches suitable for comparisons of MNOs are proposed according to different KPIs
30 such as reliability and PL.
- 31 • Our results indicate that there may be major variations in end-to-end network performances between
32 MNOs based on different geographical regions of Turkey and ordered list of reliability performance
33 comparisons of analyzed MNOs do not change when latency and PL ratio requirements vary.

34 Table 1 provides the notations and their corresponding descriptions that are used throughout the
35 remaining of the paper. Inside the paper, sets are denoted by upper case calligraphic letters such as \mathcal{N} , \mathcal{L} ,
36 etc. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we provide system model and architecture.
37 In Section 3 we provide requirements for reliability and concepts for statistical calculation analysis using
38 performance comparisons of proportions. In Section 4, we provide evaluation results for comparisons of
39 major MNOs in Turkey. Finally, in Section 5 we provide the conclusions and future work.

Table 1. Notations and their corresponding descriptions.

Notation	Description	Notation	Description
L	Number of test-site locations	γ	End-to-End Latency Target
K	Number of KPIs	s_e	Standard Error
M	Number of MNOs	N_m	Total Number of Observations for MNO-m
λ	BLER Target	P_m	PL or Reliability Ratio for MNO-m
β	Target Amount of Transmitted Data in Bytes	CI	Confidence Interval
α	Significance Level	z_x	x-quantile of $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$
$\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$	Complex Gaussian distribution with zero mean and unit variance	—	—

2. System Model and Architecture

2.1. Network Model

This paper studies 4G network performances of major MNOs using a dataset that contains KPIs such as PL, latency (due to RTT) as end-to-end performance metrics. Moreover, we also compute reliability metric by analyzing whether the general requirements based on PL, latency and transmitted data size are satisfied. Formally, we assume that there are L test-site locations, K KPIs and M MNOs in total in our system. We denote the MNO set as $\mathcal{M} = \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$, the test-site locations set as $\mathcal{L} = \{1, 2, \dots, L\}$ and the KPI set as $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$. Our focus is on comparative KPI performance differences of MNOs operating nationwide in different regions or cities. Focusing on UE level measurements, we identify the impact of location on MNO performance. To make fair comparisons for the performance, we utilize CI for the mean difference that is utilized in unpaired comparison scenarios, i.e. the case when the number of measurements over a specified region is different.

2.2. Data Collection Procedure

Figure 1 demonstrates the system level architecture for utilizing data analysis over the network performance test dataset for an example of three MNOs. As illustrated in Figure 1, data collection process for obtaining the data involves several steps. First, UEs perform the measurement tests via network performance test application installed at the mobile UE of each MNO and sends the measured KPI values into application service provider marked as data flow in step-1. The application service provider marked as step-2 has privacy preserving unit marked as step-3 which performs two main tasks: First, it generates unique test and device Identity Documents (IDs). Second, it anonymizes the data such that sensitive information such as user’s phone information, Internet Protocol (IP) addresses are eliminated for privacy preserving purposes. Both test and device IDs are used to map user sensitive information into appropriate IDs for later analysis purposes. All anonymized dataset is later kept daily in application server’s relational database marked as step-4. The pre-processing handler marked as step-5 is used for filtering, extraction, conversion or mapping purposes. For example, timezone is converted to Coordinated Universal Time (UTC), extracting MNO codes from International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) = Mobile Country Code (MCC) + Mobile Network Code (MNC) + Mobile Subscriber Identification Number (MSI) and mapping them into proper anonymized MNO names, mapping of phone model into phone categories and finding the city, district of the test location from test latitude and longitude values.

Figure 1. System architecture utilizing data analysis over the network performance test dataset.

2.3. Network Performance Analysis

As illustrated in Figure 1, network performance analysis runs the statistical methods to compare the KPI performances of MNOs. The network performance test data is extracted from application server database and is transferred into Pandas data analytics toolbox³ for further statistical analysis as marked with step-6. To determine the CI of the network performance test observations, we perform CI analysis for proportions where proportion is defined as the percentage of reliability or PL. At certain times of the month, one MNO can yield better latency or lower PL performance than other MNOs. This is expected due to randomness in number of test data samples as well as wireless network. Therefore, the statistics on such random sampled data needs to be specified in CIs. In this paper, we study an unpaired comparison case where there is no one-to-one correspondence between the network test data observations of MNOs [27]. After comparisons are calculated, data visualizations over the map are performed using Folium & Leaflet interactive maps⁴ marked as step-7 in Figure 1.

3. Reliability and Packet Loss Analysis

To compare the performance of MNOs, providing high reliability is a critical requirement for performing a stable data exchange between the UEs and the content. Reliability performance can also be a differentiating factor for MNOs. In general, 4G systems' reliability performance is good where the typical BLER

³PANDAS (2019). Pandas: Python Data Analysis Library [online]. Website <http://pandas.pydata.org/> [accessed 09 October 2019].

⁴FOLIUM (2019). Folium: Python Data Visualization [online]. Website <https://folium.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> [accessed 09 October 2019].

1 (or PL ratio in this paper) is around 10^{-2} to 10^{-3} [28]. Depending on the applications, some may also
 2 require much higher reliability together with low latency (e.g. 10 ms for some URLLC applications such
 3 as cooperative collision avoidance system (CCAS) [29]). On the other hand, it's difficult to achieve both
 4 high reliability and low latency simultaneously. For our analysis, we target to meet the following reliability
 5 requirement:

- 6 • $PL < \lambda$ for the transmission of β bytes with an end-to-end latency of γ ms.

7 3.1. CI for packet loss ratio and reliability percentages

8 To calculate unpaired PL performance comparisons of MNOs based on those collected unpaired and
 9 independent KPI- $k \in \mathcal{K}$ observations between MNOs, we compute the sample means of reliability
 10 percentages and PL ratios and then utilize statistical difference of two observations to conclude about
 11 performance advantages or weaknesses of a given MNO compared to other MNOs. For calculating PL CI,
 12 we utilize CI analysis for proportions method [27]. For proportions, we calculate the average ratio of PL
 13 at each geographic location- $l \in \mathcal{L}$ over the observation duration for all MNO- $m \in \mathcal{M}$ and KPI- $k \in \mathcal{K}$.

14 To compare two MNOs using the difference between two means of reliability and PL ratios, we
 15 utilize CI for comparative studies method. When two observations are independent of each other, the
 16 standard error for difference between two means of observations are

$$s_e^{m,n}(k,l) = \sqrt{(s_e^m(k,l))^2 + (s_e^n(k,l))^2},$$

$$\forall m, n \in \mathcal{M}, m \neq n, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L},$$

17 where $s_e^m(k,l)$ and $s_e^n(k,l)$ are the standard error of the observation KPI- $k \in \mathcal{K}$ for MNO- m and MNO- n
 18 $\in \mathcal{M}$ respectively for a given geographic location- $l \in \mathcal{L}$. The standard error is calculated as

$$s_e^m(k,l) = \sqrt{\frac{p_m(k,l)(1-p_m(k,l))}{N_m}},$$

$$\forall m \in \mathcal{M}, k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}. \tag{1}$$

19 where the PL ratio (or reliability) for N_m observations is $p_m(k,l)$ for m -th MNO and location l . If
 20 normal approximation of binomial distribution with $N_m p_m(k,l) \geq 10$ exists, the confidence interval for
 21 the PL ratio or reliability percentage can be calculated as,

$$CI_m(k,l) = p_m(k,l) \pm z_{1-\alpha/2} s_e^m(k,l),$$

$$\forall m \in \mathcal{M}, k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}. \tag{2}$$

22 where α denotes the significance level and $z_{1-\alpha/2}$ denotes $(1 - \alpha/2)$ -quantile of $\mathcal{N}(0,1)$. Thus, a
 23 confidence level of $(1-\alpha)100\%$ in calculating $CI_{m,n}(k,l)$ for the differences between two PL ratios (or
 24 reliability percentages) is given by

$$\bar{p}_m(k,l) - \bar{p}_n(k,l) \pm z_{[1-\frac{\alpha}{2}]} s_e^{m,n}(k,l),$$

$$\forall m, n \in \mathcal{M}, m \neq n, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \tag{3}$$

1 where $\bar{p}_m(k, l)$ is the average PL ratio (or reliability) over all observations. After observing the CI value
 2 of (3), if the CI contains zero within this $(1-\alpha)100\%$ confidence interval, then the statistical difference is
 3 insignificant and some conclusions cannot be drawn based on the PL (or reliability) ratios of two MNOs.

4 4. Evaluation Results

5 For evaluation results of three MNOs, anonymized data is collected offline on daily basis according to data
 6 collector process of Section 2.2 and transferred into the network performance test database for a period
 7 of 13 months ranging from January 2017 to February 2018. The statistics of the measurement tests is
 8 given in Table 2 for all MNOs which yields a relatively large sample size for fair comparisons. To obtain
 9 graphical results, we have utilized python’s seaborn statistical data visualization library⁵.

10 The network performance test measurements are done by “real users”, i.e. the users of MNOs
 11 themselves performing tests at different nationwide locations and time using the pre-installed applications
 12 on their UEs. These users measure the network performance of their MNOs at certain position (which
 13 can be enterprises, homes, airports, shopping centers, etc). Note also that not all experiments done by the
 14 users of each MNOs are using the same infrastructure, i.e. different network infrastructures (radio access
 15 network (RAN), transport and core networks). Moreover, the amount of data used for comparisons are
 16 at city-scale or nationwide.

17 4.1. Parameters for Comparisons

18 For our evaluation results, we have selected the reliability requirements for λ and γ values as the mean
 19 values PL ratios and latency respectively of all measurements in Turkey as also given in Table 2. Therefore,
 20 the average reliability of Table 2 is also given with respect to these selected values.

21 For our MNOs comparisons, without loss of generality, we have selected the numerical requirements
 22 $\lambda = 0.007$ (mean nationwide PL ratio) and $\gamma = 28.279$ ms (mean nationwide latency) for transmitting
 23 $\beta = 32$ bytes of data transmission size. Note that these requirements can also be selected to correspond to
 24 specific application requirements which is out of scope in this paper. To make fair comparisons, we have
 25 also assumed that latency is linearly proportional to transmitted data size and have updated all latency
 26 values with respect to transmission of $\beta = 32$ bytes (which is similar to 3GPP defined definition in [2]),
 27 i.e all experiments’ latency values are multiplied with a factor of $32/x_i$ where x_i is the transmitted data
 28 size of the i -th experiment.

Table 2. Nationwide network performance test data statistics in Turkey for 4G network tests.

# of measurements	648,966	# of cities	81
# of districts	890	λ , PL (avg.)	0.007
M	3	γ , Latency (avg., ms)	28.279
Reliability (avg. %)	75	Obser. Duration	13 months
Confidence level	90%	Total # of UEs	209,776

29 Table 3 shows the Coefficient of Variation (CoV) (=stdv/mean) value comparisons of PL and latency
 30 nationwide. We can observe high CoV values in PL for MNO-3 and in latency for MNO-2. The number of
 31 observations of three MNOs are 425301, 27269 and 196396 for MNO-1, MNO-2 and MNO-3 respectively.

⁵SEABORN (2019). Seaborn: Statistical Data Visualization [online]. Website <https://seaborn.pydata.org/> [accessed 09 October 2019].

Table 3. Comparisons of CoV values of observed KPIs nationwide.

CoV	MNO-1	MNO-2	MNO-3
PL	7.988	5.814	18.678
Latency	0.770	0.983	0.960

1 Figure 2 shows the violin plot of latency distributions in all Turkey using Seaborn data visualization
2 library. We can observe that median value (marked as white dot in all figures) of MNO-2 is higher than
3 other MNOs and most of the observations of all MNOs are observed to be below median values.

Figure 2. Latency violin plot of three major MNOs in Turkey.

4.2. Performance difference of MNOs across different geographical regions

5 In this subsection, we investigate the performance differences of MNOs with respect to reliability and PL
6 in different city locations of Turkey. We also visualize the CI data using Folium interactive heatmap tool.

4.2.1. Reliability Results and CI Visualizations

8 Figure 3 shows the mean difference of reliability CI comparisons of MNO-1 & MNO-2 and MNO-2 &
9 MNO-3 in selected cities of Turkey as calculated using (3). We can observe that in major cities such
10 as Istanbul and Izmir, MNO-1 performs better than MNO-2 and MNO-3 performs better than MNO-2
11 (note that similar trend is also observed in Adana). In other big city of Ankara, MNO-1 is again better
12 than MNO-2 whereas MNO-2 has better reliability than MNO-3 (note that similar trend is also observed
13 in Corum). In small cities such as Cankiri and Bitlis, we cannot conclude with 90% confidence levels
14 that MNO-1 or MNO-2 is better than one another. Moreover CI levels in those cities are higher due to
15 existence of relatively small number of observations (around 0.196% of all observations). Similarly, for
16 Mardin and Kirikkale, no decisions can be inferred when MNO-2 and MNO-3 are compared.

17 Figure 4 shows the obtained reliability versus increasing latency (ms) requirements (γ) graph for

Figure 3. Mean difference reliability CI comparisons of MNO-1 - MNO-2 and MNO-2 - MNO-3 in selected cities of Turkey when $\lambda=0.07$, $\beta=32$ bytes and $\gamma=28.279$ ms.

Figure 4. Reliability v.s. latency requirement (γ in ms) comparisons of three major MNOs in Turkey when PL rate is kept at $\lambda = 0.07$ and $\beta=32$ bytes.

Figure 5. Comparisons of reliability of MNO-2 and MNO-3 in all cities of Turkey using Folium data visualization when $\lambda=0.07$, $\beta=32$ bytes and $\gamma=28.279$ ms.

1 comparisons of three major MNOs in Turkey. Note that we have also shown CI values for each point using
 2 Eq. (2). We can easily observe that MNO-3 performs the best followed by MNO-1 and MNO-2. We can
 3 also observe that as latency requirement γ increases, the trend for performance order differences between
 4 MNOs does not change, i.e. MNO-3 performs the best followed by MNO-1 and MNO-2. Moreover,
 5 irrespective of MNO comparisons, it is observed that as the latency requirement increases, after a certain
 6 point reliability does not change. This is due to the fact that as the latency requirement is relaxed
 7 reliability increases, however after some point since the PL rate requirement λ is kept constant at 0.07,
 8 the reliability values saturate at fixed points for all MNOs.

9 For general reliability comparisons of MNO-2 and MNO-3 in all cities of Turkey, we plot Figure 5
 10 using Folium data visualization. From this figure, we can easily observe that MNO-2 is better than MNO-3
 11 in majority of cities in west and southern regions, whereas MNO-3 performs better in central regions of
 12 the country. We cannot conclude with 90% confidence level that MNO-2 or MNO-3 is better than another
 13 in eastern cities of the country which are marked with white colors.

14 4.2.2. Packet Loss Ratios and CI Visualizations

15 Figure 6 shows the obtained reliability v.s. increasing PL ratio requirements (λ) comparisons of three
 16 major MNOs in Turkey. We can observe a similar trend with Figure 4 where MNO-3 performs better than
 17 MNO-1 and MNO-2. Similarly, overall reliability performance comparison order list (i.e. the reliability of
 18 MNO-3 being better than MNO-1 followed by MNO-2) of MNOs does not change when PL requirement λ
 19 varies. Similar to observations in Figure 4 irrespective of MNO comparisons, as the PL requirement
 20 increases after a certain point, reliability does not change. This is due to the fact that as the PL

Figure 6. Reliability v.s. PL ratios requirement (λ) comparisons of three major MNOs in Turkey when latency is kept at $\gamma = 28.279$ and $\beta=32$ bytes.

Figure 7. Mean difference PL ratio CI comparisons of MNO-1 - MNO-2 and MNO-2 - MNO-3 in selected cities of Turkey.

1 requirement is relaxed, reliability increases, however after some point since the latency requirement γ
 2 is kept constant at 28.279 ms, the reliability values saturate at fixed points for all MNOs.

3 Figure 7 plots the mean PL ratio CI comparisons of MNO-1 & MNO-2 and MNO-2 & MNO-3
 4 in selected cities of Turkey. We can observe that in big cities such as Istanbul and Ankara, MNO-3 is
 5 better than MNO-2, whereas MNO-1 is better than MNO-2. Similar to Figure 3, in small sized cities

1 such as Bitlis, Mardin Corum, the CI levels are higher due to low number of observations. In some cities
2 such as Izmir, we cannot make a comparison decision with 90% confidence level for MNO-1 and MNO-2.
3 Similarly, no decision results are obtained in Yalova for MNO-2 and MNO-3 comparisons.

4 Figure 8 demonstrates the comparisons of PL ratios of MNO-1 and MNO-2 in all cities of Turkey
5 using Folium data visualization. The results indicate that in majority of cities, we cannot conclude with
6 %90 confidence level that one MNO is better than another due to existence of zero values in CIs. However,
7 in the north-west region of the country, MNO-1 performs better than MNO-2 and in central region MNO-2
8 is better than MNO-1.

Figure 8. Comparisons of PL ratios of MNO-1 and MNO-2 in all cities of Turkey using Folium data visualization.

9 5. Conclusions and Future Work

10 In this paper, we investigated the end-to-end network performance comparisons of MNOs using a crowd-
11 sourced dataset of network performance tests of each UE collected over a duration of 13 months with
12 different KPI. We utilized PL and latency values to compare reliability performances of three major
13 MNOs in Turkey. Our results indicate that significant performance differences exist across MNOs based
14 on location/region of the operating service as well the pre-set latency and PL requirements for reliability
15 analysis. Overall, we find out that ordered list of MNOs for comparative KPI performances based on
16 reliability does not change when latency and PL ratio requirements vary. As a future work, we are planning
17 to investigate the reliability comparisons corresponding to different applications such as massive machine
18 type communications, enhanced mobile broadband or ultra reliability and low latency communications
19 over 5G networks.

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